

Assessment of the Level of Application of Research Skills by Graduate Students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State, Nigeria

B. IKIROMA (Ph.D)

Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education,
Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13825826>

Abstract

This research work assessed research skills application among graduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rivers State, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design in assessing the following skills: problem identification, purposes of the study, research questions and hypotheses formulation, literature review, instrument development, report writing and communication, data collection and analysis and reference. A research question and a null hypothesis guided the study. The population of the study comprised theses/dissertations in the university. The sample used for the study consisted of 210 theses/dissertations for 2022/2023 session (110 theses and 100 dissertations) selected using stratified and simple random sampling techniques. The instrument used for the study was a 73-items, 5-points checklist tagged Graduate Students Application of Research Skills Inventory (GSARSI) which had overall reliability coefficient of 0.73 via Inter rater agreement reliability with Kappa statistic. The data collected from the sample were subjected to statistical analysis using mean, standard deviation and population t-test. The results obtained revealed that the application of research skills among graduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rivers State, Nigeria is significantly high. It was therefore recommended among others that Deans and Head of Departments or school administrator should organize regular retraining for academic staff and graduate students on different dimensions of research skills.

Key words: Assessment, Research Skills, Graduate Students, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education.

Introduction

The word research is used in everyday speech to cover a broad spectrum of meanings which makes it a confusing term for people, including graduate students, who must learn to use the word in its specialized denotation. Kelinger (1986) had defined scientific research as a systematic, controlled, empirical, and critical investigation of hypothetical propositions about the presumed relations among natural phenomena. In other words, research can be defined as the systematic process of collecting and analyzing information (data) in order to increase our understanding of the phenomena of interest. Research therefore is a process through which we attempt in achieving systematically and with the support of data the answer to a question, the resolution of a problem, or a greater understanding of a phenomenon.

The role of research is to provide a method for obtaining the answers to questions raised by inquiringly studying the evidence within the parameters of the scientific method. It is an important tool to national development, more so in education. The importance of research motivated the National University Commission (NUC) to set-up a scheme to reward good research work done by graduate students and in the year 2005 eight PhD Doctoral Theses benefited in from the award. These Doctoral Theses would not have been chosen if appropriate research skills were not found to be applied in the reports. Research, which is the systematic search and investigation for increasing the sum of knowledge of or its extended version, research and development (R & D) is the search and application of knowledge for development of new and improved products, services and industrial processes of capital development, which have in recent times, emerged in occupying the main centre stage in the activities of universities.

Considering the important role research plays in human development, both for school and in public services, it can be concluded that graduate students require adequate skills and enormous task of adding to knowledge through coherent research work the prerequisite research skills. More so, Research and Development have become the most enduring and effective means of boosting sustainable economic development. It helps to create the links between schools and industries, countries and peoples in the world, such as helping to achieve a country developmental endeavour. Furthermore, if research skills are properly applied, policy makers and other beneficiaries will have confidence in the outcome of researches, funding agencies will also be willing to support/fund such researches, since such researchers will be able to write fundable proposal, whose result shall be useful in the society and education in particular.

In the medical sector (Health sector) for instance appropriate application of research skills could lead to child mortality reduction, improve maternal health, combat HIV/AIDS malaria, and other diseases, social/political issues, such as promotion of gender equality and women empowerment, eradication of extreme poverty and hunger could be achieved through research by social sciences: Research result from education could help in achievement of Universal Basic Education in Nigeria, Furthermore, if research skills are properly applied, policy makers and other beneficiaries will have confidence in the outcome of research. It should be noted that, adequate application of research skills by researchers (graduate students) might yield reliable result that can hasten the achievement of any national government plan, such research results from faculties of science for power and energy, agriculture for research on food security, humanities education and social sciences for wealth creation, transport and security, law for Land reforms and other matters can be achieved without much difficulties.

The perception that students' performance in research examinations is not commensurate with the growing demand for good research that meet the local, national and international standards for publishing with the sole aim of contributing to the knowledge bank for national development, particularly in education, is not an over statement (Okebukola, 2002). There has been concern over the performance of students in research and development. There is a needed empirical research work to solve the degenerating nature of research skills among graduate students. It was also

discovered that some graduate students who performed excellently in their course works find it difficult to graduate after two or three years, some even abandoned their academic pursuit as a result of their inability to apply research skills appropriately. Bako (2005) observed the fact that there is an ample evidence to show that research and development generated by higher education (especially graduate students and academic staff), more than anything else, has contributed to the rise and expansion of the world knowledge, economy, and the establishment, of imperial knowledge hegemony of few countries over the rest of the world in the on-going process of globalization and its uneven development. Hence, the process of undertaking a research and skills required become necessary and important if graduate students in our universities are to contribute effectively to the society.

There is also, imperative reason why graduate students must possess the skills of research; this is because they are the same person who will eventually take over from their teachers, supervisors and academic advisers. With the present pressure on educational demands, based on the continuous increase in numbers of students seeking for admission at both undergraduate and graduate levels, these groups of future academicians, human resource developers, education directors, commissioners, etc. have a lot of task awaiting them. There is therefore the need to acquire research skills not only to get their works done for grading purpose but also to serve as good tactics, consumer's supervisors and academic advisers to the coming generations, and also to avoid having "the blind leading the blind". The deteriorating nature of student's quest for learning and the need for seasoned graduate students with adequate research skills has become imperative. More so, the graduates, after their studentship will serve the purpose of human resources in public offices it is observed also that in some universities, some graduate students abandoned their academic pursuit because of lack of research skills, either by the students directly or their academic supervisors who had no adequate knowledge of research skills. As also noted by Karani (2007, p.50) that "it was unanimously agreed by the World Bank, the national supervising agency of the universities, the National Universities Commission (NUC) of Nigeria, the Nigerian academic staff union and industries that employed graduates, that in terms of quality and quantity, the research out-put of tertiary institution in Nigeria is about the best in Sub-Sahara Africa from 1960s up to the late 1980's, but that it has declined". This is evidence that graduate students need to be equipped with adequate research skills, as a booster to this decline, hence this study.

However, Okebukola (2002, p.49) had stated earlier that "the wherewithal for research such as good research training and motivation, availability of equipment, and good library facilities pre-dominated with the onset and acceleration of the decay in the system, these ingredients (good research) faded away. That by 1996, the quantity and quality of research had declined to an all-time low". The Nigeria Universities Commission further summarizes the factors that contributed to the decline from 1988 to 1996, and subsequent collapse from 1997 to date as follows:

- (1) Lack of research skills in the modern methods.
- (2) Constraints of equipment for carrying out state-of-the art research.
- (3) Over-loaded teaching and administrations schedules with little time for research.

(4) Difficulty in accessing research funds.

(5) Diminishing scope of mentoring junior researchers by seasoned and senior researchers due to brain drain (Okehukola, 2002 p. 4).

Critically looking at these factors which have contributed to the collapse of research among academic staff is lack of research skills, if this is happening to the guardian, tutors, supervisors and academic advisers, one could imagine the status of graduate students, which the researcher may call junior researchers. In agreement with Okebukola as reflected in factor number one, which is, lack of research skills in the modern methods which the researcher of this work is out to assess, how graduate students are equipped with research skills and how they have applied the expected skills in their research works. This factor is not only mentioned, but serve as a number one pronounced or major factor crippling research work and effort in Nigeria Universities. What is this modern method of research? It is the scientific method of researching. It is sequential and consists of some identifiable steps in solving an identified problem. It involves the interplays of inductive reasoning (reasoning from specific observation and experiment to more general hypotheses and theories), and deductive reasoning (reasoning from theories to account for specific experimental results (Ali, 2007). More precisely, the ability of graduate students in possessing these scientific principles and steps are what culminated in research skills, and the extent to which graduate students apply principles is what this research is set out to discover.

Considering the importance of research to both the students, the teachers (Lecturers) and the public, it can be said that graduate students have enormous task of reporting their research findings to incoming students, teachers, community, parents, the various agencies of national development, policy makers and the society, making useful recommendations to all the benefiting members. To equip graduate students for these enormous tasks, they are at one level or the other in their schooling taught the basic skills and rudiments of research. They are expected to pass basic research methods at undergraduate and graduate levels as prerequisites for graduation and subsequent application of these skills. In addition, they are also expected to offer Advanced Research methods, Advanced Statistics to make interpretation of data easy, tests and measurement, and Educational Evaluation and some other related courses that are helpful in research work. The essence of offering such courses has been to equip them with the skills of research so that in the course of research, they could obtain valid and reliable knowledge advancement.

On the need for research skills acquisition for graduate students, Lacey (2007) recommended the survival skills in graduate work. Among her recommendations are; time management, proposal writing skills, written and oral communication skill and seeking support programmes. Time management skills; She advises graduate students to study or work on assignments at least 5 hours a day, and 35 hours a week. And establish priorities and set small goals for themselves every day. Finally daily evaluate one on how one has used ones time and how one can use time better. Proposal writing skills are a necessity. On this, she advised graduate students to investigate on campus to take workshops on proposal writing. Written and oral communication skills are critical. In her words, she states "you will present yourself as a scholar

through Journal articles, books and conference presentations” (p.4). She then advised students to seek opportunities to present their work to others. Identify conferences and try to present a paper. Seeking Support Programmes; Identification and use of resources that is available to help you develop professional skills. Support services can include research/fellowship search services, computer services, technical writing centers, and effectively teaching workshops.

In line with the need for these laudable skills, Omakaro and Popoola (2007), in a collaborative conference, both emphasized on some basic required skills on grant budget, such as; allowable and unallowable cost, budget review. Budget meetings, human subjects, traveling cost, budget justification, and that a good grant proposal should be able to answer questions from any of the enumerated items. This cannot be achieved except graduate students acquired the much-needed required research skills. Acquiring the recommended skills will help the graduate students or any researcher to obtain support programmes

What then is skill? According to Mitee and Numbere (2008, p.21) “Skill is the translation of Hebrew word "Sakal" (Pronounced Saw-kal) which means expertise or special abilities to perform tasks. Hornby (2000, p. 11) defined skill "as the ability to do well" that is, a particular ability or type of ability. There are two types of skill; super natural or innate skill and acquired skill (Mitee & Numbere, 2008, p. 22).

1. Super Natural or Innate Skills: God endows everybody with inborn skills or abilities to do certain things much better than other people. God also miraculously endows people with special skills for special purposes. For example, God gave Bezaleel the son of Uri, special skills to be the Chief Craftman of the Tabernacle (Exodus 31:3) and Aholiab and others were also given special skills to work with him (Exodus 31:6; King James version, 2006).

2. The second is acquired skills: God made man with the intellectual ability to develop inborn skills through training or learning from others. This study topic or study falls under this second aspect of skills that is acquired skills and the level of its utilization in research.

Research skills could be defined as the special abilities to undertake a careful study of a subject, especially in order to discover new facts or information about it. Research skills could also be defined as a set of abilities related to undertaking research, including strategies and tool of accessing and evaluating information. So, the abilities to follow the right principles: procedures, methodologies and otherwise of a research in order to discover new knowledge for the purpose of adding to the knowledge bank are research skills. In general, research skills in education are considered as important vehicle for promoting National developments, consciousness and cubes, and for furthering effective academic/economic independence. The government could decide to invest heavily in research works in our universities, which is to be a catalyst for development if research results of graduate students are reliable. The following are considered as adequate research skills;

A) Formulation of research problems, research questions and hypotheses. This is the ability to formulate research problem, and the subsequent ability to formulate sub-problems otherwise

known as research questions, which also lead to the genuine ability to formulate concise hypotheses in line with the problem and research questions.

B) Literature Review Skills

- i. Library Skills
- ii. Computer knowledge skill/Internet usage skills

This is to know the right procedure to evaluate work done in the area of study. This may be achieved through the use of library research skills, which help the researcher to adequately and rightly consult textbooks, encyclopedia, journals, news bulletin, etc., and the use of computer for word processing and Internet browsing

C) The skills of instrument development and validation, which is the main source of data collection.

D) Report writing and Communication Skills. This is the medium of disseminating research findings across board. A good research Instrument is also structured by writing and responses are entrance through good communication. And communication Skills which are the major tools of interaction between the researcher and his/her respondents, supervisors and even the examiners (internal and external) are necessary tools.

E) Data analysis skills. This is the application of the appropriate test statistical technique for analysis.

F) Referencing skills. This is the ability to reference other Scholars articles in a coherent and sequential order of arrangement in the main work and at the end of the work, particularly according to the America Psychological Association (APA) current edition.

The researcher draws the enumerated skills from the following reading Meinture (2002) recommends six skills, which includes: The role of literature review; Formulating research questions; Gathering data; Analysis of data; Writing a dissertation and Writing a useful readable report.

However, it is likely that different characteristics of the researcher (graduate student) may influence application of the research skills that may eventually give rise to the result obtained. This study therefore seeks to find out the influence of gender, entry qualification of graduate students and student area of specialization on the application of research skills of problem identification, research questions, and hypotheses formulation, literature review (library and internet/computer usage skills), computer usage, instrument development, communication and reporting, data collection and analysis, and referencing skills.

In theorizing this study, the concept of educational evaluation and research comes to mind. Measurement, Evaluation, Research and statistics seem to be closely related and inter-woven, and questions or questionnaires have some link on all of them. For you cannot measure without asking some vital questions, neither can you do research in any field of studies without asking some vital questions for solutions. Researching leads to measurement and evaluation, through collection of data, which is then subjected to analysis through statistical tools. It is really difficult to say exactly

which gave birth to the other (research & statistics or measurement & evaluation), but this notwithstanding, the hierarchy can be arranged as follow:

Source: Ali (2007).

The above scheme implies that, if you want to know (Research), you measure to ascertain what you want to know and when you measure, you analyze (using statistical tools) and you evaluate the information you have gathered and disseminate your findings. Consequently, some studies related to this study include those carried out by Morner (2023); E-scholarship (2016); Akanbi (2015); Lubhen and Sanders (2015); George (2016); Stein and Sandra (2016); Huffman (2018); Bondavalli (2017); Brown (2019); Forsmire (2020); Brown and Krumholz (2022); Bellard (2017); Paglia and Donahue (2023); Paul et al. (2018); Asim et al. (2005); Ashibi (2005); Okon (2019); Chen (2018); Van and Abraham (2019); Noldon and Sedlack (2018); Hines (2023).

The literature briefly reviewed had brought on issues of interest and concern. It has created the opportunity for the various questions bugging the mind of the researcher in this study. Consequently, the present study was designed to answer the following research question and the corresponding null hypothesis.

Research Question

To what extent do post graduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education apply research skills?

Hypothesis

The application of research skills by graduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education is not significantly high.

Methodology

The design for the study is survey research design. Survey research design is probably the best method available to social scientists interested in collecting original data for describing a population too large to observe directly. This research was carried out in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State Nigeria. The population is all graduate students theses/dissertations in

Nigeria and the accessible population of this study comprises all graduate students theses/dissertations of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education as at 2022/2023 session in the faculties considered. The sample for the study was 210 graduate students’ theses/dissertations drawn through stratified random sampling technique. The research instrument was a well validated checklist, titled “Graduate Students' Application of Research Skills Inventory (GSARSI)” that had overall reliability coefficient of 0.73 via Inter rater agreement reliability with Kappa statistic. The checklist was made up of 73 items with two parts. Part one was designed to obtain information from the theses/dissertations in faculties with respect to their characterization, such as gender, entry qualifications and area of specialization of students, while part two had six sections designed to collect information from the theses/dissertations with regards to each of the six components of identifiable research skills, which are: Skills of problem identification, purpose of study, research questions and hypotheses formulations; literature review skills (library research and internet usage); Instrument development skills; Report writing and communication Skills; Data collection/Analysis skills and Referencing skills. The response format for the items articulated on the checklist ranges from excellent, very good, good, average, and poor. Thus it has five points scale.

Since the study was to assess the content of theses/dissertations, the content analysis was then carried out. The researcher processed the instrument one by one while ticking accordingly the items that meet up the expected attribute per skill with the assistance of some Post Graduate students (especially those specializing in measurement, research and statistics) who were trained on the attributes to look out for per item. For easy statistical analysis, a key was developed by which information received was coded. The score a thesis/dissertation received on a particular research skill was summed on the items measuring that skill. The coding for each research skill was done respectively. Mean, standard deviation and population t-test otherwise known as one sample t-test were the statistical tools used for this study.

Results

The presentation of the data was done following the trends of the research question and the null hypothesis directing the study.

Research Question: To what extent do post graduate student in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education apply research skills?

Hypothesis: The application of the research skill among graduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education is not significantly high.

Table 1: Population t-test analysis of the extent of application of research skills among graduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education

Variables	\bar{X}	SD	t-value	df	Sig.
-----------	-----------	----	---------	----	------

Formulation of research problems, research questions and hypotheses skills	34.24	6.97	71.19*	209	.000
Literature review of library research and internet usage) skills	38.95	8.57	65.90*	209	.000
Instrument development skills	25.14	5.06	72.0*	209	.000
Data collection and analysis skills	25.97	5.74	65.57*	209	.000
Report writing and communication skills	30.83	5.52	81.00*	209	.000
Reference skills	28.10	6.01	67.76*	209	.000
Overall research skills	183.26	37.85	70.58*	209	.000

*P < 0.05, N = 210

As indicated on Table 1, the calculated t- values and the significant values of each component of research skills and the overall were all found to be less than 0.05 level of significance respectively. This shows that the application of research skills among graduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University is significantly high. The null hypothesis therefore is rejected.

Discussion

Precisely this study investigated the extent of application of research skills among graduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education in Rivers State Nigeria. The application of research skills by graduate students in the University was found to be significantly high. The result of the analysis revealed that graduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education in Rivers State, Nigeria significantly 'apply research skills. It was also noted that in each component of the skill, there was a significant application by graduate students.

From this result, what can be said about graduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education generally is that their application of research skill is high and that they properly apply the skills in their graduate research work. Though the result is coming out as a surprise against the popular notion that graduate students' theses/dissertations cannot be relied upon, as such research results are hardly consulted to solve problems of education and national issues. Many graduate students that were not able to meet the requirement do give impression that the research process is extremely difficult to embark upon. Conclusively graduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education in Rivers State, Nigerian have applied research skills efficiently and coherently in their theses/dissertations. This may not be unconnected to the fact that thesis/dissertation is the final required standard examination to be met a degree is conferred on the individual. So graduate

students' put on extra effort to meet up with the set standards. Another factor that could account for this could be the fact that the graduate boards at the various Departments and levels put effort to see that theses/dissertations are corrected before approval, such as the departmental and faculty graduate boards, in their attempt to produce qualitative graduates in thinking, learning and doing, they emphasize intellectual rigor and creativity to their graduate students. This finding is in agreement with Asim et al. (2007) who discovered that the science graduates' theses are not implicated in any aspect where the practical skills displayed in the reports are below expectation or marginally good. This they attributed to the efforts of graduate students who do everything within their resources to satisfy the requirement of graduate school.

In contrast to this finding is the research work conducted by Morner (2023) specifically on library research skill, who discovered that doctoral students were unprepared to conduct dissertation literature reviews, because they were not equipped with library research skills. It was however true that all the characteristics of graduate students may not apply these skills equally. It became necessary that certain of their characteristics be studied further in relation to how they have affected the application of these skills of research. The result is thus presented as follows. The application of research skills among graduate students is moderately high.

On each component the result shows that the graduate students' application of literature review was higher than the application of the other five research skills. While the application of the skills of instrument development was the least to be applied efficiently and appropriately. The reason for this may not be farfetched. Graduate students are taught the importance of literature review and authors. In line with Afolabi (2022) who emphasized on the importance of literature review to research procedure. The recent development in information and communication technology may have aided the literature review of graduate students. On instrument development skill, specific studies on this particular skill are not common in literature, perhaps it is neglected but the findings in this study will go a long way to help other researchers.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study, the researcher concludes that graduate students have benefited from the teaching they went through during course work, especially in research methods, statistics, measurement, evaluation and metric in their various faculties. Also the compulsory seminar courses and attendance to conference has helped them in a great deal.

On the basis of the finding of this study, the following recommendations are made;

1. Universities administrators, National University Commission (NUC) officers, Directors of research and development, Ministers/Commissioners should give adequate attention to tertiary education including funding/monitoring of research work in our universities. For example, the governments (State and Federal) should give research grants to academic staff of universities, who will in turn incorporate graduate students in undertaking such research, while NUC follow up to ensure that such grants are properly utilized.

2. Deans and H.O.Ds of the various faculties/departments should put more efforts to redeem quality research work in their departments/faculties.
3. University administrators should see the need to introduce ICT centres and digital libraries in our universities.
4. Lecturers in education, especially those of them in measurement, research and statistics should be deployed to teach in other faculties.
5. Seminars and workshops should be organized on a regular basis for graduate students to update their skills in research work and to encourage them to embark on research.

References

- Afolabi, M. (2022). The review of related literature in research. *International Journal of Information and Library Research*, 10(1), 59-66.
- Akanbi, H.A. (2015). Business mathematics and quantitative skills. Gap Between theory and practice in the polytechnic curriculum. *The Journal of Nigeria Association of Technology*, 10 (2), 14-15.
- Akpan, S.M. (2006). *Research critic guidelines for graduate students*. A material given to graduate on evaluation of research and research tools. University of Calabar, Calabar.
- Ali, H.O. (2007). *The origin of questionnaire, scales of measurement and their special significance in measurement and evaluation*. Seminar paper presented to students and staff of Department of Educational Foundation, Guidance and Counselling, University of Calabar, Nigeria.
- Ali, H.O. (2005). *Understanding the historical and philosophical foundations of science*. Port Harcourt: Pre- Joe Publisher.
- Asim, A. E., Kalu, I. M., Idaka, I. E., & Basse, W. S. (2007). *Competency in STM Assessment: The case of primary school teachers in Cross River state of Nigeria*. An international conference to review research on science, technology and mathematics education proceedings.
- Asim, E. A., Kalu, K., & Ekwueme, C. O. (2005). Skills in unpublished graduate theses end research in science education. *International Journal Series on Tropical Issues*, 8 (1), 89-94.
- Ashibi, N. (2005). *Assessment of the application of testing skills among secondary school teachers in Northern Cross State of Nigeria*. An Unpublished M.Ed thesis. University of Calabar, Nigeria.
- Bako, S. (2005). *University research and development in Nigeria: Time for a paradigmatic shift*. Paper prepared for 11th General Assembly of CORDESRIC, on rethink African Development, Beyond Impasse.
- Bellard, L.M. (2017). Information literacy needs of non-traditional graduate students in social work. *Research Strategies*, 20 (4), 494-505.
- Bondavalli, V. (2017). *Foundations of measurement: Measurement theories*. http://www.portal.acm.org/citatio.cfm/theories_of_measurement.
- Brown, C.M. (2019). Information literacy of physical science graduate in the information age. *College & Research Libraries*, 60 (5), 426-438.
- Brown, C.M. & Krumhoz, L.R. (2022). Integrating information literacy in to Science-curriculum. *College & Research Libraries*, 63 (2), 111-123.

- Chen, J. F. (2018). *Gender differences in Taiwan business writing errors*. rs/.occor. edu/tw/[].
- Denga, D.I. & Ali, A. (1998). *An introduction to research methods and statistics in education and social sciences*. Rapid Educational Publishers.
- E-scholarship @ BC (2016). *A test of library research skills for education doctoral students: A digital commons project*. <http://escholarship.Bc.Edu/dissertations/AA19329299>.
- Forshire, M. (2020). Bibliographic instruction in Physics Libraries: a survey of current practice and tips for marketing BI. *Science and Technology Libraries*, 19 (2), 25-34.
- George, C. (2016). *Scholarly use of information: Graduate student's information research*. <http://information.net/ir/11-4/paper272.html>.
- Hines, D. (2023). Admissions criteria for ranking master's level applicants to clinical doctoral programs. *Teaching of Psychology*, 133, 64-67.
- Hoffman, K., Antwi-Nsiah., Feng, V. & Stanisy, M. (2018). *Library research skills: A need assessment for graduate students' workshop*. Allyn & Betty Taylor Library.
- Hornby, A.S. (2000). *Advanced learner dictionary of current English (6" .ed)*. Oxford University Press.
- Joshua, M.T. (2005). *Fundamentals of test and measurement in education*. University of Calabar Press.
- Karani, F.A. (2007). *Higher education in Africa in the 20th century*. A paper presented at the Africa Regional consultation preparatory to the world conference on higher education. Dakar, May 18.
- Kelinger, F.N. (1986). *Foundations of behavioral research*. Halt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Lacey, L. (2007). *Survival skills in graduate research*. <http://gradschool.Nmsu.Edu/fellowships/index.htm>.
- Lubben, F. & Sandra, K. (2015). Developing research skills in mathematics, science and technology educators in southern Africa: The role of a professional organization. *Journal of International Corporation in Education*, 8 (3), 81-91.
- Meinture, C. (2002). *The art of the action research in classroom*. David Fulton
- Mitee, L.M. & Numbere, N.E. (2008). *Sunday school lessons*. Greater Evangelism World Crusade Publications.
- Morner, C. J. (2023). *A test of library research skills for education doctoral students*. <http://escholarship.Bc.Edu/dissertations/AA19329299/>
- Noldon, D. & Sedlacck, K. (2018). *Gender differences in attitudes, skills and behaviours among academic talented university freshman*. <http://www.questia.com/google.W.E.Scholarqst:jserssionid>.
- Okebukola, P. (2002). *The state of university education in Nigeria*. National University Commission.
- Okon, A. E. (2019). *The influence of sex of teachers on the performance of students in practical in secondary schools in Calabar municipal council*. Unpublished B.Ed project, University of Calabar, Nigeria.
- Omokaro, D. N. (2007). *On theory and practice of good grants man ship*. A paper presented in a conference for graduate students. University of Calabar, Calabar, August 5.
- Paglia, A. & Donahue, A. (2023). Collaboration works: Integrating information competencies into the psychology curricula. *Reference Service Review*, 31 (94), 330-328.

- Paul, R., Elder, L. & Bartell, T. (2018). *Study of 38 public universities and 28 private universities to determine faculty emphasis on critical instruction*. <http://www.critical.org> the critical thinking community.
- Popoola, I. (2007). *Typical format of a research proposal*. A paper presented in conference organized for graduate students, University of Calabar, August 5.
- Stein, J. & Sandra, T. (2016). A preliminary report on the value of the Internet and the library in graduate students' research. *Performance Measurement Matrices*, 7 (2),107-115.
- Van, R. & Abraham, R. (2019). Strategies of unsuccessful learners. *Teachers of English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL) Quarterly*, 24, 176- 182.